

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTEROPERABILITY OF GEODATA IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF CADASTRE SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The article provides a comprehensive study of the interoperability of geospatial data in the context of the digital transformation of cadastral systems, which is a key direction for the modernization of spatial management and land administration in the context of the development of e-government. The essence of the concept of interoperability and its implementation at four basic levels: technical, semantic, organizational, and legal, is analyzed. Based on the study of international standards, tools for ensuring the compatibility of data structures, terminology, metadata, and exchange procedures between cadastral systems and other geoinformation registers have been identified.

The study focuses on data models, in particular the Land Administration Domain Model, which ensures the unification of cadastral information and its integration with other spatial databases. Modern approaches to the implementation of technical interoperability using WMS, WFS, REST API, and GML formats are identified. Examples of the implementation of interoperable cadastral platforms in European Union countries are given, and the state of implementation of relevant approaches in Ukraine is analyzed, in particular, using the example of the Public Cadastral Map, the Unified State Electronic System in the field of construction, and the development of the UA-LADM model.

As a result of the study, a generalized scheme for the implementation of geodata interoperability in the national cadaster was developed and recommendations were formulated for further harmonization of standards, development of interagency cooperation, and improvement of regulatory and legal regulation of geodata exchange. The need for an interdisciplinary approach to ensuring interoperability was identified, taking into account the requirements of openness, accuracy, reliability, and continuous updating of spatial information in land administration systems.

Keywords: geodata interoperability; digital transformation; cadastral system; open data; cadaster; spatial data; geographic information system; national geospatial data infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the digital transformation of land relations, the issue of interoperability of geospatial data in cadastral systems is of particular importance. Modern requirements for ensuring sustainable development of territories, transparency of land management, and efficiency of administrative services pose new challenges for the organization of exchange, processing, and integration of spatial information.

As cadastral systems in different countries gradually transition to electronic platforms with open software interfaces, compliance with the principles of interoperability — the ability of systems to exchange, interpret, and reuse spatial information without loss of content — becomes an essential issue.

Interoperability in the field of geodata means the harmonization of formats, metadata, database structures, and the regulatory environment governing the exchange of information between public authorities, the private sector, and the public.

This applies to technical standards as well as semantic, organizational, and legal compatibility. The successful implementation of these principles in cadastral systems opens up new opportunities for building a unified geoinformation space in which all entities have access to up-to-date, structured, and reliable information about land parcels, legal status, restrictions on use, and other important attributes.

Important technological catalysts for such a transformation are geoinformation systems, ISO TC/211 and INSPIRE standards, as well as approaches to data integration through APIs, web services, ontologies, and platforms such as Spatial Data Infrastructure. For example, as part of the European INSPIRE initiative, technical requirements for geospatial data structures and formats have been created to ensure cross-national compatibility of cadastral information. Similar principles are currently being implemented in Ukraine, as evidenced by projects to open cadastral APIs, integrate with the Unified State Electronic System in the field of construction, and other e-government services.

The purpose of this article is to systematize concepts and approaches to ensuring the interoperability of geodata within the framework of the digital transformation of cadastral systems. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of technical, semantic, and organizational levels of interoperability, the consideration of national and international examples, as well as the identification of the main challenges, prospects, and conditions for the formation of an open cadastral ecosystem capable of effectively interacting with other digital platforms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of geodata interoperability in cadastral systems is studied at the intersection of information technology, land administration, geoinformatics, and law. Leading international studies emphasize the need to create a single space for geoinformation resources that ensures compatibility and reuse of data by different structures. Particular importance is attached to the implementation of ISO 19100 standards and the INSPIRE directive, which defines the technical and semantic basis for the exchange of spatial data in the European Union [1].

Thus, Rajabifard et al. (2019) examine the concept of “cadastral interoperability” in the context of building a national spatial data infrastructure (NSDI). The authors emphasize that the effective integration of cadastral and other geodata requires a unified approach to metadata, formats, exchange interfaces, and legal provisions for data access [2].

The study by Lemmen and Van Oosterom (2020) justifies the need to transition to data models based on the LADM (Land Administration Domain Model) concept. This model, standardized as ISO 19152, allows for the unification of cadastral information structures and their interaction with other spatial data sources [3]. According to the authors' conclusions, the implementation of LADM significantly simplifies the implementation of interoperable services, in particular through APIs and web services.

In the context of the digital transformation of cadastral systems in EU countries, the results of the publication by Cromptoets et al. (2021) are particularly noteworthy, as they analyze the level of interoperability of geodata in state land use systems. The authors identify four levels of interoperability: technical, semantic, organizational, and legal, each of which requires separate strategies and implementation mechanisms [4].

Kraak and Brown (2022) emphasize the importance of compatibility of cartographic symbols, coordinate systems, and language ontologies within semantic interoperability [5]. This ensures technical data transfer and preserves the semantic accuracy of information when different institutions interact.

In recent years, Ukraine has been gradually adapting to global practices. Sergienko and Knyzh (2022) examine the experience of implementing a geoportal of open cadastral data in Ukraine and emphasize the advantages of using REST API for convenient access to information about land plots [6]. In addition, Palamarchuk's (2021) study on interoperability barriers in

the Ukrainian land cadastre, particularly in terms of legal regulation and incompatibility of source data formats, is also relevant [7].

Thus, an analysis of scientific sources shows that interoperability is a complex characteristic of cadastral systems, covering the technological component as well as semantic, organizational, and legal compatibility. Ensuring interoperability requires an interdisciplinary approach, data standardization, infrastructure integration, and, most importantly, system openness.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research into the interoperability of geodata in cadastral systems requires a comprehensive approach that covers the analysis of technical, regulatory, and organizational aspects of spatial data integration. The materials for analysis include: open cadastral portals, national and international standards for geospatial data exchange, examples of service-oriented architecture implementation, documentation for the State Land Cadastre of Ukraine, as well as publications by leading scientists in the field of GIS and cadastre [8–11].

The methodology is based on an analysis of the functional capabilities of platforms that implement interoperability principles at different levels:

1. Technical level — analysis of the syntactic compatibility of data structures (XML, GML, JSON, GeoJSON), service types (WMS, WFS, REST API), and exchange standards (OGC, ISO 19100).

2. Semantic level — comparison of glossaries, attribute schemas, and object models (LADM, INSPIRE Cadastral Parcel Schema) used in different jurisdictions.

3. Organizational level — assessment of inter-agency coordination, exchange procedures, and regulations for integrating cadastral information with other registries.

4. Legal level — study of restrictions and norms regarding openness, personal data protection, and reuse of geoinformation.

As an example, the following geoportals were analyzed in detail: the National Cadastral System of Ukraine, Lantmäteriet (Sweden), Kadaster (Netherlands), and INSPIRE Geoportal (EU) were analyzed in detail, with their services evaluated according to the following parameters: exchange formats, interface types, access level, relevance, and compliance with ISO/OGC standards.

For comparative analysis, a method of expert questioning of 10 specialists in the field of cadastral administration and GIS was used. The questionnaire assessed parameters such as:

- API openness (availability of documentation, REST interfaces),
- data model compatibility (LADM, proprietary formats),
- automated exchange (support for transactional WFS or similar services),
- integration with other platforms (real estate registries, construction system, tax block),
- availability of feedback, validation, and change monitoring services.

The survey results were processed using RStudio and QGIS software, including cluster analysis, rating

scales, and the construction of data flow diagrams between services. Spatial modeling was performed using PostgreSQL/PostGIS, which made it possible to create a generalized model for the exchange of cadastral data at the TG level.

At the final stage, methods of critical analysis of regulatory documents were applied, including the Law of Ukraine “On National Geospatial Data Infrastructure,” Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, INSPIRE technical guidelines (EU Regulation No. 1089/2010), as well as reference materials from ISO TC/211.

Similar approaches have been successfully applied in previous studies, in particular in the works of

Van Loenen et al. (2018), who analyzed the practice of geodata exchange between cadastral and municipal systems [5], and Gisinger et al. (2020), who highlighted the issue of building interoperable SDIs using the example of Germany [6].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

An analysis of current approaches to ensuring the interoperability of geospatial data in cadastral systems has made it possible to identify the main components of digital transformation. The results of the study show that the implementation of interoperable technologies depends on four interrelated levels: technical, semantic, organizational, and legal, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Basic levels of geodata interoperability in cadastral systems

At the technical level, it has been found that the most widely used services are WMS, WFS, and WCS in accordance with OGC specifications, as well as REST API, which support GeoJSON, GML, XML, and CSV formats. In European cadastral practice, these services are used as a basis for the exchange of spatial information between cadastral authorities, local authorities, banks, notaries, etc. [1].

For example, Kadaster Netherlands provides an open WFS for obtaining cadastral parcel boundaries in GML format with automated connectivity via QGIS, ArcGIS, or third-party services. A similar implementation has been in place in Ukraine since 2022 — the State Service of Ukraine for Geodesy, Cartography and Cadastre has provided a REST API for requesting information about land parcels by cadastral number [2].

The semantic level involves the unification of data structures, terminology, and object models. The most common model that enables this unification is LADM (ISO 19152), which allows the legal status of land parcels, property relations, restrictions, and easements to be described in a standardized form [3].

The implementation of LADM in national cadastral models is currently underway in Poland, Spain, Kenya, Colombia, and the Philippines. In Ukraine, its adaptation is just beginning — in 2023, as part of the World Bank's Land Reform Support Program, a project model of cadastral data based on LADM (UA-LADM Core Model) was created, which takes into account the specifics of registration of rights in the DRRPNM, as shown in Figure 2 [4].

Fig. 2. Example of a fragment of a logical model of LADM objects in the Ukrainian context

The organizational level of interoperability involves the creation of stable exchange procedures, agreement on formats, and mechanisms for interaction between authorities. The experience of Estonia, Sweden, and Denmark shows that for the effective functioning of the geoinformation space, it is necessary to establish centralized metadata management, maintain exchange logs, and provide object identifiers within the entire state system [5].

In Ukraine, a positive example is the integration of the Public Cadastral Map with the building register through the Unified State Electronic System in the Field of Construction (USESFC), which allows for the automated retrieval of information about permits, technical conditions, and engineering networks in JSON format, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Scheme of organizational interaction between the cadastral system, the Unified State Electronic System for Cadastral and Land Registration and the State Register of Real Estate

The legal basis for ensuring interoperability lies in defining the data access regime, reuse licenses, API rights, personal data, and transfer restrictions. The INSPIRE Directive requires public authorities to make data available for reuse in machine-readable form and to ensure transparency regarding its origin [1].

According to the Law of Ukraine “On National Geospatial Data Infrastructure” (No. 554-IX), open geodata must be made public through metadata and access services, which is in line with European requirements [12]. A number of executive acts detail the technical requirements for services, identifier formation, change monitoring, and user authentication, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Legal basis for access to cadastral geodata in accordance with INSPIRE and Ukrainian legislation

The result of interoperability implementation is improved decision-making at the community and state levels. For example:

- GeoHub Denmark provides full integration of cadastral, address, topographic, and demographic data in real time;

- GeoCadastre UA (pilot development in 2024) is an experimental system in Ukraine that allows the integration of cadastral layers with the register of property rights and urban planning documentation at the TG level.

These examples confirm that the full implementation of interoperability principles automates requests, increases the transparency of land registration, reduces the time required to obtain services, and eliminates duplication of information.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The interoperability of geospatial data is a fundamental factor in the effective digital transformation of cadastral systems. The study identified four interrelated levels of interoperability — technical, semantic, organizational, and legal — each of which requires clear standards, coordination mechanisms, and regulatory support.

At the technical level, the key factors are the implementation of OGC-based services (WMS/WFS/REST API), unified data formats (GeoJSON, GML), and support for integration through open interfaces. Semantic compatibility is achieved through the adaptation of international models (in particular, LADM), which provide a unified structure for cadastral object attributes. Organizational integration requires constant exchange between state registries, coordination of updates, and automated data validation. Legal interoperability requires open access to data, protection of personal information, and the creation of conditions for the reuse of geoinformation.

The practical implementation of these approaches in Ukraine began with the API of the Public Cadastral Map, the introduction of the EDESSB, and the development of UA-LADM models. Successful international examples, such as Kadaster Netherlands, GeoHub Denmark, and INSPIRE Geoportal, demonstrate how open standards and compatibility policies contribute to the formation of a unified digital space for decision-making.

Prospects for further research include:

- the development of open cadastral platform architectures with support for transactional services;

- integration with automated services for registration of rights, urban cadaster, and environmental monitoring;

- use of ontological modeling technologies to enhance semantic interoperability;

- formation of a unified national open geodata policy based on the principles of INSPIRE and the Open Data Charter.

Thus, geodata interoperability is not just a technical or formal concept, but a key condition for building effective, transparent, and adaptive land management in the context of digital transformation.

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